

INTEGRATING FRAM AND BAYESIAN NETWORKS FOR RISK ASSESSMENT IN AIR TRAFFIC CONTROL

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Abstract: *The Air Traffic Control (ATC) system is about to change significantly in the coming years due to increased traffic demand and the introduction of advanced automation tools and emerging technologies. In this context, using efficient methods for risk assessment is crucial to enable proactive safety management and ensure the continued maintenance of an adequate level of safety. These methods should address increased system complexity, dynamic interactions, and uncertainty in future operations. Conventional approaches may not be able to cover the potential new behaviors and interdependencies characteristic of socio-technical systems such as ATC. This research introduces a hybrid methodological framework that combines the Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) and Bayesian Belief Networks (BBN) in the risk assessment of a future ATC system. The main idea of this research is to assess the safety of the future ATC system from a strategic perspective with particular emphasis on the increasing role of automation in the work of Air Traffic Controllers (ATCOs) and its impact on the overall functioning of the ATC system. To understand different interactions between various system's elements, the first part of the research includes the analysis using the FRAM method as a new alternative to traditional safety assessment. The second part of the research applies the BBN method for quantitative assessment and evaluation of variability obtained from FRAM analysis. FRAM is a qualitative method that identifies system functions and interactions between them, while BBN is a probabilistic graphical model that represents uncertain relationships between variables. A combination of those two approaches can contribute to a more comprehensive analysis of the safety of a complex system using both qualitative and quantitative data. FRAM provides cause and effect relationships and the possible performance variability, while BBN quantifies these relationships, enabling probabilistic analysis and supporting data-driven safety assessment. They provide both functional understanding and numerical evidence to define potential safety improvements.*

Keywords: *Risk assesment, Functional Resonance Analysis method, Bayesian networks, air traffic control.*